

Reactions of later 3d divalent transition metal chlorides with metal alkoxides and characterization of novel heterobimetallic alkoxide coordination compounds

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Abstract : The interesting and somewhat unexpected solubilization of insoluble anhydrous divalent transition metal chlorides, MCl_2 ($M = Co, Ni$ and Cu) in benzene in the presence of $Ti(OEt)_4$ or $Zr(OPr^i)_4$ or $Al(OPr^i)_3$ in 1 : 2 and 1 : 4 molar ratios, followed by usual workup yields quantitatively, novel complexes of the general formulae $MM'_x(OR)_{4x}Cl_2$ [where $M = Co, M' = Ti$ ($x = 2, R = Et$) (1); $M = Co, M' = Ti$ ($x = 4, R = Et$) (2); $M = Co, M' = Zr$ ($x = 2, R = Pr^i$) (3); $M = Co, M' = Zr$ ($x = 4, R = Pr^i$) (4); $M = Ni, M' = Ti$ ($x = 2, R = Et$) (5); $M = Ni, M' = Ti$ ($x = 4, R = Et$) (6); $M = Ni, M' = Zr$ ($x = 2, R = Pr^i$) (7); $M = Ni, M' = Zr$ ($x = 4, R = Pr^i$) (8); $M = Cu, M' = Ti$ ($x = 2, R = Et$) (9); $M = Cu, M' = Ti$ ($x = 4, R = Et$) (10)] and $CoAl_2(OPr^i)_6Cl_2$ (11). All of these complexes are highly moisture-sensitive coloured solids, soluble in typical organic solvents and have been successfully characterized by elemental analysis, spectroscopic and magnetic studies as well as by molecular weight measurements.

Keywords : Heterobimetallic alkoxides, transition metal alkoxides, cobalt(II) alkoxides.

Innovations in synthetic strategies continue to open new vistas in heterometallic alkoxide chemistry¹ and establish new fields of study. Although during last 25 years notable advances have been made in the study of heterometallic alkoxides of later 3d transition metals^{2,3}, yet reactions of their metal chlorides with different homometal alkoxides to the best of our knowledge appear to have not been investigated prior to our present studies. Our group continues to have a strong interest in heterometallic alkoxide coordination compounds of later 3d transition metals^{2,3} and in this context, we have been successful in devising new synthetic approaches^{1h,4,5}, which allowed access to a variety of novel products with interesting structural, spectroscopic and magnetic properties. We report in this paper for the first time the results of our investigations on the reactions of later 3d transition metal chlorides with different metal alkoxides, which led to the formation of structurally interesting compounds. Investigations in this particular area assume importance, because heterometallic alkoxides can be used as single-source precursors to mixed-metal oxides with high technology applications^{6,7}.

Results and discussion

Reactions at room temperature in 1 : 2 and 1 : 4 molar ratios of metal chlorides MCl_2 [$M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}$,

and Cu^{II}] with $Ti(OEt)_4$ or $Zr(OPr^i)_4$ or $Al(OPr^i)_3$ in benzene resulted in dissolution of the metal chlorides within 10–20 h. From the resulting solution, after removal of excess solvent novel heterobimetallic alkoxide chlorides have been isolated in quantitative yields according to two general reactions as illustrated in eqs. (1) and (2).

	M	M'	x	R
(1)	Co	Ti	2	Et
(2)	Co	Ti	4	Et
(3)	Co	Zr	2	Pr ⁱ
(4)	Co	Zr	4	Pr ⁱ
(5)	Ni	Ti	2	Et
(6)	Ni	Ti	4	Et
(7)	Ni	Zr	2	Pr ⁱ
(8)	Ni	Zr	4	Pr ⁱ
(9)	Cu	Ti	2	Et
(10)	Cu	Ti	4	Et

All these new compounds (Table 1) are highly moisture-sensitive, coloured solids, soluble in typical organic solvents (e.g. benzene, toluene, tetrahydrofuran). Determinations of molecular weights (ebullioscopically/cryoscopically) in benzene solution depict monomeric nature for **2**, **4**, **6**, **8**, **10** and **11** while **1**, **3**, **5**, **7** and **9** are dimeric.

Spectral studies :

Derivatives **1-11** exhibit structurally important infrared absorptions^{3-5,8} in the regions : 1120–1180 $\nu(\text{OPr}^i)$, 1100–1160 $\nu(\text{OEt})$, 900–1085 $\nu(\text{C-O})$, 665–672 $\nu(\text{Al-O})$, 540–570 $\nu(\text{Ti-O})$, 510–515 $\nu(\text{Zr-O})$, 410–490 cm^{-1} $\nu(\text{M-O})$ [M = Co, Ni, Cu].

The electronic absorption spectra (Table 2) of cobalt(II) complexes **1-4** and **11** show main absorption bands centred in the 17065–17985 cm^{-1} region ascribable to $\nu_3[{}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)]$ transition with a distinct shoulder on the high frequency side in the 18180–18590 cm^{-1} region arising from spin-forbidden transition. In addition, weak bands as shoulder centred in the 15150–15510 cm^{-1} region due

to $\nu_2[{}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}]$ transition have also been observed. These absorptions are consistent in terms of octahedral cobalt(II) (d^7 high-spin) complexes^{4,5,9}. Interestingly, **1-4** and **11** also show characteristic ligand to metal [Cl \rightarrow Co^{II}] charge transfer (LMCT) transition^{9a} in the visible region 28570–33900 cm^{-1} . The absorption due to $\nu_1[{}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}]$ transition in near infrared region is out of the range of the equipment used.

Nickel(II) (d^8 high-spin) complexes **5-8** display two moderately intense bands with maxima centred in the regions 12050–12910 cm^{-1} $\nu_2[{}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}]$ and 22670–23260 cm^{-1} $\nu_3[{}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)]$, which is consistent with an octahedral model^{4,5,9}. These complexes **5-8** also display strong ligand to metal [Cl \rightarrow Ni^{II}] charge transfer transition in the 31250–33330 cm^{-1} region. The values of ν_1 as well as that of Racah parameter β were calculated by the equation given by Underhill and Billings¹⁰.

Spectra of copper(II) (d^9) complexes **9** and **10** exhibit a single broad band maxima centred in the region 12195–14085 cm^{-1} , which is characteristic of a ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ tran-

Table 1. Preparative, analytical and some physical data for chloride alkoxide complexes **1-11**

Products ^a	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)				M. wt. Found (Calcd.)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
	Co/Ni/Cu	Ti/Zr/Al	Cl	OEt/OPr ⁱ		
Yield (g, %), colour						
[CoTi ₂ (OEt) ₈ Cl ₂] (1)	9.95	16.18	12.03	61.38	1185	5.32
(2.60, 89); dark blue	(10.05)	(16.34)	(12.10)	(61.50)	(586)	
[CoTi ₄ (OEt) ₁₆ Cl ₂] (2)	5.52	18.21	6.74	69.02	1060	5.34
(3.59, 93); dark blue	(5.65)	(18.38)	(6.80)	(69.16)	(1042)	
[CoZr ₂ (OPr ⁱ) ₈ Cl ₂] (3)	7.38	23.11	8.90	60.08	1590	5.37
(1.40, 86); purple	(7.51)	(23.24)	(9.03)	(60.22)	(785)	
[CoZr ₄ (OPr ⁱ) ₁₆ Cl ₂] (4)	3.96	25.17	4.85	65.50	1456	5.40
(2.78, 90); purple	(4.09)	(25.34)	(4.92)	(65.65)	(1440)	
[NiTi ₂ (OEt) ₈ Cl ₂] (5)	9.83	16.06	11.87	61.33	1192	3.18
(3.20, 88); reddish-yellow	(10.01)	(16.34)	(12.10)	(61.53)	(586)	
[NiTi ₄ (OEt) ₁₆ Cl ₂] (6)	5.52	18.09	6.69	68.82	1075	3.21
(4.30, 92); reddish-yellow	(5.63)	(18.38)	(6.80)	(69.18)	(1042)	
[NiZr ₂ (OPr ⁱ) ₈ Cl ₂] (7)	7.42	23.08	8.98	60.05	1590	3.24
(1.32, 78); light yellow	(7.48)	(23.25)	(9.04)	(60.24)	(785)	
[NiZr ₄ (OPr ⁱ) ₁₆ Cl ₂] (8)	3.98	25.12	4.85	65.48	1463	3.25
(2.22, 80); yellow	(4.08)	(25.34)	(4.92)	(65.66)	(1440)	
[CuTi ₂ (OEt) ₈ Cl ₂] (9)	10.70	16.06	11.95	60.89	1200	2.00
(2.00, 88); greenish-brown	(10.76)	(16.21)	(12.00)	(61.02)	(591)	
[CuTi ₄ (OEt) ₁₆ Cl ₂] (10)	5.92	18.14	6.70	68.71	1072	2.04
(3.16, 90); greenish-brown	(6.07)	(18.29)	(6.77)	(68.86)	(1047)	
[CoAl ₂ (OPr ⁱ) ₆ Cl ₂] (11)	10.82	9.96	13.07	65.74	1095	5.42
(1.75, 83); dark blue	(10.95)	(10.02)	(13.17)	(65.86)	(538)	

^aCompounds **1**, **3-10** are solids and compounds **2** and **11** are sticky solids.

Table 2. Electronic spectral (cm^{-1}) data and molar extinction coefficients ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$) for new complexes

(a) Cobalt(II) derivatives :

Compd.	Absorption maxima		LMCT
	${}^4T_{1g} \xrightarrow{\nu_2} {}^4A_{2g}(F)$	${}^4T_{1g} \xrightarrow{\nu_3} {}^4T_{1g}(P)$	
(1)	15267 (sh)	17985 (80.00)	29940 (202.50)
(2)	15508 (sh)	17857 (91.67)	28571 (113.33)
(3)	15151 (sh)	17094 (50.00), 18181 (sh)	33898 (41.00)
(4)	15503 (sh)	17543 (65.00), 18518 (sh)	31446 (120.00)
(11)	15479 (sh)	17123 (72.50), 18181 (sh)	31746 (102.50)
	15385 (sh) (dichloromethane)	17065 (81.00), 18590 (sh)	31250 (109.00)

(b) Nickel(II) derivatives :

Compd.	${}^3A_{2g} \xrightarrow{\nu_1} {}^4T_{2g}(F)$	${}^3A_{2g} \xrightarrow{\nu_2} {}^3T_{1g}(F)$	${}^3A_{2g} \xrightarrow{\nu_3} {}^3T_{1g}(P)$	$10 Dq$	B	β	LMCT
	(5)	7624	12690 (15.00)	22727 (25.00)	7624	836	
(6)	7753	12903 (25.00)	23095 (40.00)	7753	849	0.81	32051 (275.00)
	7130 (dichloromethane)	12050 (16.00)	23260 (44.00)	7130	928	0.89	31750 (190.00)
(7)	7703	12788 (20.00)	22676 (30.00)	7703	824	0.79	33333 (200.00)
(8)	7714	12821 (16.67)	22831 (33.33)	7714	834	0.80	31250 (267.00)

(c) Copper(II) derivatives :

Compd.	${}^2E_g \longrightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$	LMCT
	(9)	
(10)	14084 (76.04)	20618 (88.71)
	14025 (86.67) (dichloromethane)	20880 (119.33)

sition for a distorted octahedral geometry around copper(II)^{4,5,9}. Furthermore, both these complexes also display ligand to metal [Cl→Cu^{II}] charge transfer transitions¹¹ in the 20615–20880 cm^{-1} region. Electronic spectra of some typical complexes have also been recorded in dichloromethane, which followed the same pattern already recorded in benzene. For example, in dichloromethane the observed absorptions for three representative complexes are given below : **6** : 7130 ν_1 , 12050 (16.00) ν_2 , 23260 (44.00) ν_3 , 31750 (190.00) LMCT; **10** : 14025 (86.67) and 20880 (119.33) LMCT; **11**: 15385 (sh) ν_2 , 17065 (81.00) and 18590 (sh) ν_3 , 31250 (109.00) LMCT.

Magnetic studies :

The magnetic susceptibilities of the complexes have

been measured at room temperature. The magnetic moment data (Table 1) for complexes **1-4** fall in the 5.32–5.40 B.M. range, in agreement with the expected values for high-spin octahedral cobalt(II) (d^7) complexes¹². Nickel(II) complexes **5-8** exhibit magnetic moments in the 3.18–3.25 B.M. range, which are consistent with those reported for six-coordinated high-spin d^8 nickel(II) complexes¹³. The magnetic moments of the d^9 copper(II) complexes are 2.00 for **9** and 2.04 B.M. for **10**, indicating high-spin distorted octahedral geometry.

On the basis of aforementioned spectroscopic (IR and UV-vis), magnetic and molecular weight data as well as taking into consideration, the X-ray crystallographically established structure¹⁴ of $[\text{Mg}\{\eta^4\text{-Ti}_2(\text{OEt})_8\text{Cl}\}(\mu\text{-Cl})]_2$, an analogous six-coordinated geometry for cobalt(II),

nickel(II) and copper(II) in complexes **1**, **3**, **5**, **7** and **9** involving tetradentate ligation of $\{\text{Ti}_2(\text{OEt})_8\text{Cl}\}^-$ and $\{\text{Zr}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_8\text{Cl}\}^-$ is more plausible. In complexes **2**, **4**, **6**, **8**, **10** and **11** a tridentate ligating mode of $\{\text{Ti}_2(\text{OEt})_8\text{Cl}\}^-$, $\{\text{Zr}_2(\text{OPr}^i)_8\text{Cl}\}^-$ and $\{\text{Al}(\text{OPr}^i)_3\text{Cl}\}^-$ is consistent with the observed electronic spectral and magnetic data, which favour for an octahedral geometry for the concerned metal ions.

Experimental

All reactions and subsequent manipulations were performed under extreme anhydrous conditions, using oven dried (150–160 °C) glass apparatus with standard quickfit joints. Benzene (b.p. 80 °C), toluene (b.p. 110 °C), *n*-hexane (b.p. 68 °C) and tetrahydrofuran (b.p. 67 °C) were dried and distilled from sodium benzophenone ketyl immediately prior to use. Ethyl alcohol (b.p. 78 °C) and isopropyl alcohol (b.p. 82 °C) were distilled from calcium hydride. $\text{Ti}(\text{OEt})_4$ and $\text{Zr}(\text{OPr}^i)_4$ were prepared by ammonia method³. Titanium and zirconium were determined as their oxides (TiO_2 or ZrO_2). Estimations¹⁵ of cobalt, nickel and copper were performed by complexometric titration, by gravimetric method as bis(dimethylglyoximate)nickel(II) and iodometrically, respectively. Chloride and alkoxy groups (ethoxy or isopropoxy) were determined by Volhard's¹⁵ and oxidimetric¹⁶ methods. IR spectra (4000–400 cm^{-1}) were recorded on a FT-IR spectrophotometer as Nujol mulls using CsI optics. Electronic spectra were recorded on a UV-visible Bio 50 spectrophotometer. The magnetic susceptibilities were measured at room temperature by the Gouy method on a Polytronic Gouy magnetic balance (EMP 75), using $\text{HgCo}(\text{CNS})_4$ as calibrant and correcting for diamagnetism with the appropriate Pascal constants. The magnetic moment data for the new complexes (Table 1) were calculated by the equation $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 2.84 (X^{\text{corr}}_{\text{M}} \cdot T)^{1/2}$. Molecular weights were determined cryoscopically/ebullioscopically in benzene solutions.

Synthesis of novel heterobimetallic alkoxide-chloride derivatives :

Due to similarity in synthetic procedures for the new derivatives and also for the sake of brevity, preparative details of only three typical compounds are given below :

$[\text{NiTi}_2(\text{OEt})_8\text{Cl}_2]$ (**5**) :

The anhydrous NiCl_2 (0.80 g, 6.17 mmol) was treated with an excess of ethyl alcohol and stirred at room temperature for ~8 h, during which time clear pale-green solution was obtained. Volatiles were removed under reduced pressure to yield the precursor complex $\text{NiCl}_2 \cdot x$

EtOH as a pale-green solid. To this solid was added benzene (~25 ml) and the resulting suspension was stirred at room temperature for 2 h, followed by addition of $\text{Ti}(\text{OEt})_4$ (2.81 g, 12.32 mmol) dissolved in benzene (~10 ml). The resulting reaction mixture was then stirred at room temperature for 12 h and finally refluxed for 5 h, during which the colour of the reaction mixture changed from pale-green to dark yellow. Removal of volatiles under reduced pressure afforded the title complex **5** as a dark yellow solid (3.59 g, 99%). Recrystallization from *n*-hexane at -20 °C yielded dark yellow solid product (3.20 g, 88%).

Adopting a procedure similar to **5**, derivatives **1**, **2**, **6**, **9** and **10** were also prepared using required quantities of the reactants as shown below for each compound :

- (1) CoCl_2 (0.65 g, 5.01 mmol) and $\text{Ti}(\text{OEt})_4$ (2.29 g, 10.04 mmol)
- (2) CoCl_2 (0.48 g, 3.70 mmol) and $\text{Ti}(\text{OEt})_4$ (3.37 g, 14.77 mmol)
- (6) NiCl_2 (0.58 g, 4.47 mmol) and $\text{Ti}(\text{OEt})_4$ (4.08 g, 1.79 mmol)
- (9) CuCl_2 (0.52 g, 3.87 mmol) and $\text{Ti}(\text{OEt})_4$ (1.77 g, 7.76 mmol)
- (10) CuCl_2 (0.45 g, 3.35 mmol) and $\text{Ti}(\text{OEt})_4$ (3.06 g, 13.41 mmol)

$[\text{CoZr}_4(\text{OPr}^i)_{16}\text{Cl}_2]$ (**4**) :

To a suspension of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot x \text{Pr}^i\text{OH}$ {freshly prepared by stirring anhydrous CoCl_2 (0.28 g, 2.16 mmol) in isopropyl alcohol (~20 ml) at room temperature for ~6 h, followed by removal of solvent under reduced pressure} in benzene (~25 ml) was added $\text{Zr}(\text{OPr}^i)_4$ (2.83 g, 8.64 mmol). The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 18 h, followed by refluxing for ~8 h, during which colour of the solution changed from blue to dark blue. The excess solvent was removed under reduced pressure to obtain the compound **4** as a dark blue solid (2.78 g, 90%), which was recrystallized from *n*-hexane at -20 °C in 2.78 g (90%) yield.

Similar procedure was employed to prepare derivatives **3**, **7** and **8**. The quantities of reactants used are shown below for each compound :

- (3) CoCl_2 (0.27 g, 2.08 mmol) and $\text{Zr}(\text{OPr}^i)_4$ (1.37 g, 4.18 mmol)
- (7) NiCl_2 (0.28 g, 2.16 mmol) and $\text{Zr}(\text{OPr}^i)_4$ (1.42 g, 4.33 mmol)
- (8) NiCl_2 (0.25 g, 1.93 mmol) and $\text{Zr}(\text{OPr}^i)_4$ (2.53 g, 7.72 mmol)

$[CoAl_2(OPr^i)_6Cl_2]$ (11) :

The anhydrous $CoCl_2$ (0.51 g, 3.92 mmol) was treated with isopropyl alcohol (50 ml) and the resulting suspension was stirred at room temperature for 10 h. Removal of volatiles under reduced pressure afforded blue solid product $CoCl_2 \cdot xPr^iOH$, to which was added benzene (~40 ml) and then stirred at room temperature for 2 h. $Al(OPr^i)_3$ (1.61 g, 7.88 mmol) was then added to the blue suspension of $CoCl_2 \cdot xPr^iOH$ in benzene. The resulting reaction mixture was then stirred at room temperature for 15 h, followed by refluxing for 4 h, during which dark blue clear solution was obtained. Volatiles from the solution were removed under reduced pressure to obtain dark blue solid (1.00 g, 95%), which was recrystallized from *n*-hexane at $-20^\circ C$ in 1.75 g (83%) yield.

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